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ABSTRACT

This study examined the avifauna diversity of Covenant University Ota South Western Nigeria. The study area was divided into three blocks based on their different land use types. A total of 30 counting stations was used, and 10 stations per each study site. Counting bands of 50m radius was used for all the stations. Forty one bird species were recorded in the Developed Area, Sixty six (66) bird species in the Farmland and fifty (98) species encountered in the forest area. In all, a total of 104 bird species belonging to 33 families and 13 orders were recorded, The Order Passeriformes had the highest frequency (56 %) of the entire number of birds recorded, while the dominant family was Pycnonotidae, comprising (9.2 %) of the total species One rare bird species, Grosbeak weaver and 3 species of the malimbe were recorded From the result of the relative abundance of bird species obtained Pied Crow has the highest of (0.74) followed by Cattle Egret (0.53) in the Developed Area, Black Headed Weaver has the highest (0.16) followed by Cattle Egret (0.14) in the Farm Land while Common Bulbul had the highest in the Fallow Area. The Developed Area had the highest relative abundance of (1.723), Fallow Area (0.474 and Farmland (0.437). From the result obtained on the bird species diversity index Fallow Area had the highest diversity index in both seasons of the 4.218 in the dry season and 3.893 in the wet season while Developed area had the lowest 3.298 and 2.6.

Key Words: Home Range, Urban Development, Avian Species, Agricultural intensification and Habitat Fragmentation.

INTRODUCTION

Birds are among the best monitors of environmental changes and have been used to evaluate the environment throughout the history as bio-monitors and the changes in their population, behavior patterns and reproductive ability have most often been used to examine the long term effects of habitat fragmentation. Hence they are the good indicators of ecological status of any given ecosystem (Castelletta, et al, 2000). Forests attract a large number of avifauna because of the habitat suitability for most of them. This especially include the birds that are associated with the vegetation, and for most, the existence of trees is vital to their life cycle. Birds show different levels of interest to various stands depending on the age of the stands Deforestation in the tropics is one of the major threats to global biodiversity (Dobson et al. 1997). The relationship between species diversity and its components, richness and evenness, has been receiving increased attention (Mass and Dietsch, 2004). Boulinier, et al. (1998) has proposed that changes in diversity may be mediated by changes in one or the other component and that these changes reflect alternative environmental conditions. He suggests that diversity changes with richness in relatively stable, benign environments and varies with evenness under unstable, rigorous conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Area

Covenant University is located in Ota the headquarters of Ado/Ota local government area of South Western Nigeria. It has total land mass of 2,800 hectares, which include the church area and the university farms. It has central coordinates of 6°41'00"N and 3°41'00"E. Annual rainfall is between 1000 and 1200ml. February and March are the driest months and the wettest months are July and September. The mean annual temperature is 30°C. The mean

annual relative humidity is not below 25% in the driest months and 100% during the wet seasons (Mengistu, and Salami .2007). The vegetation is a mixture of southern Guinea savanna, riparian, with Guinea-Congo Forest affiliation and open, cultivated or fallow fields. Within the university the economic trees, fruits trees were not cut down and various species of ornamental trees are well laid out such a way that it is eco-friendly. Notable trees in the study area are *Azalia africana*, *Terminalia ivorensis*, *Terminalia superba*, *Spondia mombin*, *pycananthus angolensis*, *Musanga ceropioides*, *Ceiba pentandra*, *Chrysophyllum albidum*, *Irvengia gabolensis*, *Irvengia wombolu*, *Hidergardia bateri*, *Acacia scorpioide s* and *Ficus spp*s (Keay, 1989).

Data Collection

The study was carried out in three blocks with different land use, including the fallow area, farmland and developed which include the school area and Canaan land within the study area. Counting stations or predefined spots were established in roosting sites, wetland and feeding sites as well as forest edges. Counting bands of 50m radius was used for all the stations. The minimum distance between two counting stations was 200m. The number of counting stations was determined by the site size. In all 30 counting station were used, 10 stations per a study site.

On arrival at the sites birds were allowed time to settle before recording all the birds seen or heard for a predetermined time.(20 minutes). Bird calls were also recorded with a voice recorder and played back later for confirmation. Physical features of birds sighted but could not be identified immediately were taken and field guide book of West African birds (Burrow and Demey, 2011) was used to identify the bird species and bird calls was used to confirmed the presence of nocturnal bird species within the study sites. Data was collected for six months three months in the dry season (November, February and March) and three months in the wet season (June, August and September) in 2014

From the data collected, avian species diversity was calculated using Shannon diversity index, (Usher, 1991) which is given as:

$$H^i = - \sum P_i \ln P_i$$

Where: H^i = diversity index

P_i = is the proportion of the i th species in the sample

$\ln P_i$ = is the natural logarithm of the species proportion.

Species Relative Population Density

The relative population density of bird species at various sites and seasons were determined as outlined by Bibby *et al.*,(1992) as follows:

$$D = \frac{n_1 + n_2 \text{Log}_e \left[\frac{n_1 + n_2}{n_2} \right]}{\pi r^2 m}$$

where: D = density

r = radius of the first zone

n_1 = number of birds counted within zone

n_2 = number of birds counted beyond zone and m = number of replicate count in such area.

Data collected from the observations were explored with descriptive statistics and analyzed with analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 17 (SPSS, 2008).

RESULT

A total of 98 bird species belonging to 33 families and 13 orders were recorded in the study area. The Order Passeriformes had the highest frequency (56 %) of the entire number of birds recorded, while the dominant family was *Pycnonotidae*, comprising (9.2 %) of the total species. The record of the bird species in the three land use type revealed that the developed Area has a total of 41 bird species belonging to 24 families and 8 orders, Farm Land has 66 bird species belonging to 29 families and 11 orders while, the Fallow Area which is a secondary ecosystem has 98 bird species belonging to 33 families and 13 orders. 7 bird species were observed to be intra African migrants, 8

Palaearctic migrants and 83 resident bird species. Individual relative abundance of bird species in the Developed Area shown that Pied Crow (*Corvus albus*) was the highest (0.74) this was followed by Cattle Egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) 0.53. In the Farmland Black Headed Weaver (*Ploceus melanocephalus*) has the highest relative abundance of 0.16 followed by Cattle Egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) with relative abundance of 0.14 while, the Fallow Area the bird species with highest relative abundance is Common Bulbul (*Pycnonotus barbatus*) 0.14 followed by Bronze Mannikin (*Spermestes cucullatus*) with relative abundance of 0.13. From the result obtained on the bird species diversity index Fallow Area had the highest diversity index in both seasons of the 4.218 in the dry season and 3.893 in the wet season while Developed area had the lowest 3.298 and 2.6 (Tables 4 and 5).

Table 1: Bird Species Composition in the Study Area

Location	Family	Species	Order
Developed Area	24	41	8
Farm Land	29	66	11
Fallow Area	33	98	13

Figure 1: Family Composition of Bird Species in the Study Area

Figure 2: Exclusive and Bird Species Common to the Three Blocks in the Study Area

Figure 3: Status of Bird Species in the Study Area

Table 3: Diversity of Bird Species in the Study Area during Dry Season

Diversity Index	Developed Area	Farmland	Fallow Area
Taxa_S	37	70	85
Individuals	228	1107	367
Dominance_D	0.05359	0.02567	0.01845
Shannon_H	3.298	3.946	4.218
Evenness_e^H	0.7311	0.7392	0.799
Margalef	6.631	9.844	14.22

Table 4: Diversity of Bird Species in the Wet Season in the Study Area

Diversity Index	Developed Area	Farmland	Fallow Area
Taxa_S	24	44	63
Individuals	188	214	340
Dominance_D	0.1139	0.03961	0.02614
Shannon_H	2.6	3.521	3.893
Evenness_e^H	0.5608	0.7684	0.7787
Margalef	4.392	8.013	10.64

DISCUSSION

The research study revealed that this environment support diverse bird species. The result obtained from research study indicates abundant birdlife in the Fallow Area and Farmland. The differences in bird species diversity and abundance in the different land use types may be due to land use changes and forest heterogeneity which bring about variation in the availability of food, cover, predation risk and micro –climatic variation which is supported by various authors Cody (1985) reported the level of distribution of bird species in habitat is normally as a result of an occurrence of plant species that support their population and to variation in species-specific requirements in the choice of habitat. This is also consistent with Mangnall and Crowe, (2003) stated that the distribution of bird species is largely dependent on the availability of food, water and cover. Different groups of bird species seem to respond differently to different land uses. Insectivores are known to be an indicator of noticeable responses to land use. This

result is consistent with work of Matlock Jr et al. (2003) who reported that forest patches and protected area in Sao Tome have high retention of bird species than agricultural landscapes. Furthermore, it has been reported that multi-strata tropical agroforestry systems support high bird diversity and populations than arboreal vegetation (Greenberg et al. 2000; Faria et al. 2006; Bos et al 2007). The number of bird species recorded in the Developed area was lower than the two rest blocks, and this suggest that human disturbance in populated areas alters bird species richness (Pearson, 1977), as they avoid predation. Similarly, Herkert (2009) reported that the loss of habitat to urbanization reduces the quality of the remaining vegetation thus affect the population of avian species in the area.

The relative abundance of avian species in the study area was higher in the farmland than the rest study sites. This agrees with previous work by Kormar (2006) who also reported high abundance of bird species in cultivated areas, which could be due to food availability. From the result of the relative abundance obtained Pied Crow (*Corvus albus*) (0.74) and Cattle Egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) (0.53) which were highest in the Developed Area, Black Headed Weaver (*Ploceus melanocephalus*) (0.14) and Cattle Egret (0.13) in the Farmland while, Common Bulbul (*Pycnonotus barbatus*) (0.14) and Bronze Mannikin (*Spermestes cucullatus*) (0.13) in the Fallow Area is consistent with result obtained by Best et al, (1990) that the extent of change in bird species composition and abundance depends on the specificity of each bird species habitat requirement, in other words the species tolerance to changes to its environment. Species with restricted habitat changes pattern are more vulnerable to changes in land use practices than those occupying a wider variety of environment.

Avian behavioral pattern was found to play a big role in bird diversity and distribution among the three areas sampled (Cody 1985). For example, Red Headed Malimbe (*Malimbus erythrogaster*), Saker Falcon (*Falco cherrug*) and Western Nicator *Nicator chloris* were sighted only in the Fallow Area within the study area. The result indicates there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in avian species diversity between the blocks in both seasons of the year. Some savanna bird species were encountered in the forest area which suggests that human disturbance is ongoing in the study sites; therefore land use change could result in the decline rare species in the area (Manu, 2000). This is consistent with the findings of MacArthur and MacArthur (2001) who reported that avian diversity increases with vegetation complexity. Pearson (1997) also reported that tropical wet evergreen forest support more rare bird species than other habitats. This suggests that the availability of nesting site is one of the principal factors that determine the structure of bird community in agricultural landscape (Soderstrom et al., 2003).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Bird species diversity was higher in the Fallow Area than farmland and school area within the study area which suggests that land use change between the three blocks was responsible for this.

The study area is surrounded by large settlements and the people in the area are involved in logging, majorly cutting down commercial timber species such as *Ceiba pentandra*, *Alstonia congensis*, *Cola gigantea*, *Daniella ogea*, *Urban expansion and deforestation*. Selective logging of tree species in this area should be properly managed so that avian habitats can be supported. Land conversion for agricultural purposes is very high in this region, since most of the communities are agrarian. However, this may increase extinction risk for many threatened and endangered birds in the area, such as *Grosbeak Weaver Tockus fasciatus*, *Lamptornis purpureiceps*, *Malimbus scutatus* and *Thescelocichla leucopleura*. The management of these areas should design programmes to discourage bush burning, livestock grazing, deforestation and illegal farming in the forest area.

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REFERENCES

- Best, L.B., Whitmore, R.C., Booth, G.M. (1990) Use of cornfields by birds during the breeding season: the importance of edge habitat. *American Midland Naturalist* 123: 84-99.
- Bibby, C.J. Buagess N.D., Hail D.A. (1992) *Birds census techniques* 1st edition. Academic Press, London. 1 – 8pp.
- Bos, M. M., Steffan-Dewenter, I. and Tscharrntke, T. (2009) The contribution of cacao agroforests to the conservation of lower canopy and beetle diversity in Indonesia. *Biodiversity Conservation* 16:2429-2444.
- Boulinier, T., J. D. Nichols, F. R. Sauer, J. E. Hines, and K. H. Pollock. 1998. Estimating species richness: the importance of heterogeneity in species detectability. *Ecology* 79: 1018–1028.

- Brooks, T. M., R. A. Mittermeier, C. G. Mittermeier, G. A. B. da Fonseca, A. B. Rylands, W. R. Konstant, P. Flick, J. Pilgrim, A. Oldfield, G. Magin, and C. Hilton-Taylor. 2002. Habitat loss and extinction in the hotspots of biodiversity. *Conservation Biology* 16:909–923.
- Brooks, T., S. L. Pimm, and J. O. Oyugi. 1999b. Time lag between deforestation and bird extinction in tropical forest fragments. *Conservation Biology* 13:1140–1150. Brooks, T., J. Tobias, and A. Balmford. 1999c. Deforestation and bird species extinction in the Atlantic forest. *Animal Conservation* 2:211–222.
- Brown, K. S., and G. G. Brown. 1992. Habitat alteration and species loss in Brazilian forests. Pages 119–142 in T. Whitmore and J. A. Sayer, editors. *Tropical deforestation and species extinction*. Chapman and Hall, London, UK.
- Borrow, Nik and Demey Ron. (2012). “A guide to the birds of western Africa”. Princeton University Press.
- Castelletta, M., N. S. Sodhi, and R. Subaraj. 2000. Heavy extinctions of forest avifauna in Singapore: lessons for biodiversity conservation in South-East Asia. *Conservation Biology* 14:1870–1880.
- Cody, M.,L.,(1985) An introduction in habitat selection in birds. *In* Habitat selection in birds (Cody ed.) Academic Press Inc., London pp 191-248.
- Dobson, A. P., A. D. Bradshaw, and A. J. M. Baker. 1997. Hopes for the future: restoration ecology and conservation biology. *Nature* 277:515–521.
- Faria, D., Paciencia, M., L., B., Dixo, M., Laps, R., R. & Baumgarten, J. (2007) Ferns, frogs, lizards, birds and bats in forest fragments and shade cacao plantations in two contrasting landscapes in the Atlantic forest, Brazil. *Biodiversity and Conservation*. 16:2335-2357.
- Greenberg, R., Bichier, P., Angón, A.C. (2000) The conservation value for birds of cacao plantations with diverse planted shade in Tabasco, Mexico. *Animal Conservation* 3: 105-112
- Herkert, J.R. (2009) Response of bird populations to farmland set-aside programs. *Conservation Biology* 23: 1036-1040.
- Keay,R.W.J.,(1989), *Trees of Nigeria. A review version of Nigerian trees (1960, 1964)* by R. W. J Keay, C. F. A Onochie and D. P Strandfield. Claridon Press Oxford University press: Pp 476 pp.
- MacArthur R. H. and MacArthur J. W. (1999). On bird species diversity. *Ecology* 42, 594 - 598.
- Mangnall M.J. & Crowe T.M. (2003) The effecte of agriculture on farmland bird assemblage on the Agulhas plain, Western Cape, South Africa. *African journal of Ecology* 41, 266-276.
- Manu, S.A., (2000) Effects of habitat fragmentation on the distribution of forest birds in south western Nigeria with particular reference to the Ibadan Malimbés and other Malimbés, PhD thesis. University of Oxford.
- Mengistu, and Salami . (2007). Application of remote sensing and GIS inland use/land cover mapping and change detection in a part of south western Nigeria. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* Vol. 1 (5), pp. 099 -109.
- Pearson D. (1977) Pantropical comparison of bird community: structure of six lowland forest sites, *Condor* 79: 232-244.
- Poudevigne, I., and J. Baudry. 2003. The implication of past and present landscape patterns for biodiversity research: introduction and overview. *Landscape Ecology* 18:223– 225.
- Söderström, B., Kiema, S. and Reid, R. S. (2003): Intensified agricultural land-use and bird conservation in Burkina Faso. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* 99: 113-124.
- Sutherland,W.J. (2009). *From Individual Behaviour to Population Ecology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

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APPENDIX1

Relative Abundance of Bird Species in the Study Area

Specie	Family	DA		FL		FA		Total
		IND	RA	IND	RA	IND	RA	
African Crane	Rallidae			2	0.002	3	0.004	0.006
African Cuckoo Hawk	Accipitridae			1	0.001	2	0.002	0.003
African Dwarf Kingfisher	Alcedinidae					1	0.001	0.001
African Emerald Cuckoo	Cucunidae					3	0.004	0.004
African Green Pigeon	columbidae					7	0.009	0.009
African Grey Hornbill	Bucerotidae	2	0.002	3	0.004	4	0.005	0.011
African Harrier Hawk	Accipitridae					3	0.004	0.004
African Jacana	Jacanidae					2	0.002	0.002
African Pied Hornbill	Bucerotidae	4	0.005	3	0.004	5	0.006	0.015
African Thrush	Turdidae	6	0.007	2	0.002	3	0.004	0.013
Amethyst Sunbird	Nectariniidae	2	0.002					0.002
Assorges Greenbull	Pycnonotidae					2	0.002	0.002
Black Coucal	Cucunidae			3	0.004	4	0.005	0.009
Black Headed Weaver	Ploceidae	21	0.28	12	0.16	24	0.32	0.76
Black Kite	Accipitridae	3	0.004	2	0.002	5	0.006	0.012
Black Shouldered Kite	Accipitridae			2	0.002			0.002
Black Spinetail	Apodidae	6	0.007					0.007
Blue Bellied Roller	Coraciidae			1	0.001	2	0.002	0.003
Blue Breasted Kingfisher	Alcedinidae			1	0.001	2	0.002	0.003
Blue Spotted Wood Dove	columbidae			3	0.004	5	0.006	0.011
Blue Grey Heron	Ardeidae					2	0.002	0.002
Blue Throated Roller	Coraciidae			1	0.001	2	0.002	0.003
Broad Billed Roller	Coraciidae	3	0.004	4	0.005	5	0.006	0.015
Bronze Mannikin	Estrildidae			8	0.009	10	0.013	0.022
Black winged Sliit	Recurvirostridae					2	0.002	0.002
Buff- Throated Sunbird	Nectariniidae	3	0.004					0.004
Bush Petronia	Passeridae			3	0.004	2	0.002	0.006
Cattle Egret	Ardeidae	40	0.53	11	0.014	9	0.012	0.79
Collard Sunbird	Nectariniidae					2	0.002	0.002
Common Bulbul	Pycnonotidae	2	0.002	4	0.005	12	0.016	0.023
Common Wattle eye	Platysteiridae	2	0.002			1	0.001	0.003
Common Kestrel	Falconidae	3	0.004			1	0.001	0.005
Copper Sunbird	Nectariniidae	2	0.002					0.002
Didric Cuckoo	Cucunidae			2	0.002	3	0.004	0.006
Double Spurred Francolins	Phasianidae			5	0.006	8	0.009	0.015
Fork Tailed Drongo	Dicruridae	2	0.002			3	0.004	0.006
Green Headed Sunbird	Nectariniidae	3	0.004			1	0.001	0.005
Green Combec	Sylviidae					2	0.002	0.002

Green Hylia	Sylviidae					2	0.002	0.002
Green Sunbird	Nectariniidae	1	0.001					0.001
Grey Backed Camaroptera	Cisticonidae			4	0.005	6	0.007	0.012
Grey Headed Bush Shrike	Malaconotidae					2	0.002	0.002
Grey Headed Sparrow	Passeridae	9	0.012	6	0.007	3	0.004	0.023
Grey Kestrel	Falconidae	2	0.004			1	0.001	0.005
Grosbeak Weaver	Ploceidae					6	0.007	0.007
Klass Cuckoo	Cucunidae			1	0.001	2	0.002	0.003
Laughing Dove	columbidae	15	0.02	8	0.009	3	0.004	0.015
Little Bee Eater	Meropidae			3	0.004	5	0.006	0.01
Little Greenbul	Pycnonotidae					2	0.002	0.003
Little Sparrow Hawk	Accipitridae	2	0.002					0.002
Lizard Burzard	Accipitridae			3	0.004			0.004
Malachite kingfisher	Alcedinidae					3	0.004	0.004
Mouse Brown Sunbird	Nectariniidae	2	0.002					0.002
Northern Puffback	Malaconotidae	1	0.001			2	0.002	0.003
Northern White faced owl	Strigidae	3	0.004					0.004
Northern Red Bishop	Ploceidae			6	0.007	9	0.012	0.019
Orange Cheeked Waxbill	Estrildidae			5	0.006	8	0.009	0.015
Pale Fronted Negrofinch	Estrildidae					2	0.002	0.002
Pied Crow	Corvidae	56	0.74	5	0.006			0.75
Pin Tailed Whydah	Viduidae	6	0.007	4	0.005	2	0.002	0.014
Plain Backed Pipit	Motacillidae	3	0.004			3	0.004	0.008
purple Headed Glossy Starling	Sturnidae	2	0.002	4	0.005	2	0.002	0.009
Plain Greenbul	Pycnonotidae					3	0.004	0.004
Red Bellied Firefinch	Estrildidae	2	0.002	3	0.004			0.006
Red Billed Helmet Shrike	Prionopidae					2	0.002	0.002
Red Billed Paradise Flycatcher	Muscicapidae					3	0.004	0.004
Red Eyed Dove	columbidae	5	0.006	6	0.007	4	0.005	0.018
Red Headed Bluebill	Estrildidae					2	0.002	0.002
Red Headed Malimbe	Ploceidae					4	0.005	0.005
Red Vented Malimbe	Ploceidae					6	0.007	0.007
Rufous Crested Swallow	Hirundinidae			6	0.07			0.007
Senegal Coucal	Cucunidae			3	0.004	4	0.005	0.009
Senegal Eremomela	Sylviidae					2	0.002	0.002
Senegal Thick Knee	Burhinidae					2	0.002	0.002
Senegal Woodland Kingfisher	Alcedinidae	6	0.007	4	0.005	2	0.002	0.014
Simple Leaflove	Pycnonotidae			2	0.002	2	0.002	0.004
Short winged Cisticola	Cisticonidae			3	0.004			0.004
Singing Bush Lark	Alaudidae					2	0.002	0.002
Sooty Boubou	Melaconotidae					1	0.001	0.001
splendid Sunbird	Nectariniidae	2	0.002					0.002

Standard Winged Nightjar	Caprimulgidae			2	0.002			0.002
Tawny Flanked Prinnia	Cisticonidae			3		5	0.006	0.006
Tree Pipit	Motacillidae			1	0.001	2	0.002	0.003
Variable Sunbird	Nectariniidae	2	0.002	1	0.001			0.001
Viellot weaver	Ploceidae	5	0.006	4				0.006
Village Weaver	Ploceidae	26	0.034	10	0.012	6	0.007	0.053
Western Nicator	Pycnonotidae					2	0.002	0.002
Whinchat	Muscicapidae			3	0.004	3	0.004	0.008
Whistling Cisticola	Cisticonidae			1	0.001	2	0.002	0.003
Western Grey Plantain Eater	Musophagidae	3	0.004	5	0.006	3	0.004	0.014
White Faced Whistling Duck	Anatidae					8	0.009	0.009
White Tailed Lapwing	Charadriidae			5	0.006	12	0.016	0.022
Woodchat Shrike	Laniidae					2	0.002	0.002
White Throated Bee Eater	Meropidae	2	0.002	4	0.005	7	0.008	0.015
Yellow Breasted Apalis	Cisticonidae					2	0.002	0.002
Yellow Throated Lonclaw	Motacillidae			5	0.006	2	0.002	0.008
Yellow Wagtail	Motacillidae	3	0.004	4	0.005	3	0.004	0.009
Yellow whiskered Greenbull	Pycnonotidae					1	0.001	0.001
Yellow white Eye	Zosteropidae					1	0.001	0.001
Yellow Winged Hyliota	Sylviidae					3	0.004	0.004
Yellowbill	Cuculidae					5	0.006	0.006

Legend: DA- Developed Area, FL- Farm Land, FA- Fallow Area; IND- Individual Bird Species, RA- Relative Abundance

APPENDIX 2

Checklist of Bird Species in the Study Area

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name
Accipitridae	<i>Aviceda cuculoides</i>	African Cuckoo Hawk
	<i>Polyboroides typus</i>	African Harrier Hawk
	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	Black Kite
	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	Black Shouldered Kite
	<i>Accipiter minullus</i>	Little Sparrow Hawk
	<i>Kaupifalco monogrammicus</i>	Lizard Buzard
Alaudidae	<i>Mirafra cantillans</i>	Singing Bush Lark
Alcedinidae	<i>Ispidina lecontei</i>	African Dwarf Kingfisher
	<i>Halcyon malimbica</i>	Blue Breasted Kingfisher
	<i>Alcedo cristata</i>	Malachite kingfisher
	<i>Halcyon senegalensis</i>	Senegal Woodland Kingfisher
Anatidae	<i>Dendrocygna viduata</i>	White Faced Whistling Duck
Apodidae	<i>Telacanthura melanopygia</i>	Black Spinetail
Ardeidae	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Blue Grey Heron
	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Cattle Egret
Bucerotidae	<i>Tockus nasutus</i>	African Grey Hornbill

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name
	<i>Tockus fasciatus</i>	African Pied Hornbill
Burhinidae	<i>Burhinus senegalensis</i>	Senegal Thick Knee
Caprimulgidae	<i>Macrodipteryx longipennis</i>	Standard Winged Nightjar
Charadriidae	<i>Vanellus leucurus</i>	White Tailed Lapwing
Cisticonidae	<i>Camaroptera brachyura</i>	Grey Backed Camaroptera
	<i>Cisticola brachypterus</i>	Short winged Cisticola
	<i>Prinia subflava</i>	Tawny Flanked Prinnia
	<i>Cisticola lateralis</i>	Whistling Cisticola
	<i>Apalis flavida</i>	Yellow Breasted Apalis
Columbidae	<i>Treron calva</i>	African Green Pigeon
	<i>Turtur brehmeri</i>	Blue Spotted Wood Dove
	<i>Streptopelia capicola</i>	Laughing Dove
	<i>Streptopelia semitorquata</i>	Red Eyed Dove
Coraciidae	<i>Coracias cyanogaster</i>	Blue Bellied Roller
	<i>Eurystomus gularis</i>	Blue Throated Roller
	<i>Eurystomus glaucurus</i>	Broad Billed Roller
Corvidae	<i>Corvus albus</i>	Pied Crow
Cuculidae	<i>Chrysococcyx cupreus</i>	African Emerald Cuckoo
	<i>Centropus grillii</i>	Black Coucal
	<i>Chrysococcyx caprius</i>	Didric Cuckoo
	<i>Chrysococcyx klaas</i>	Klass Cuckoo
	<i>Centropus senegalensis</i>	Senegal Coucal
	<i>Ceuthmochares aereus</i>	Yellowbill
Dicruridae	<i>Dicrurus adsimilis</i>	Fork Tailed Drongo
Estrildidae	<i>Spermestes cucullatus</i>	Bronze Mannikin
	<i>Estrilda melpoda</i>	Orange Cheeked Waxbill
	<i>Nigrita luteifrons</i>	Pale Fronted Negrofinch
	<i>Spermophaga ruficapilla</i>	Red Headed Bluebill
	<i>Lagonosticta rubricata</i>	Red Bellied Firefinch
Falconidae	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	Common Kestrel
	<i>Falco cherrug</i>	Saker Falcon
	<i>Falco biarmicus</i>	Lanner Falcon
	<i>Falco ardosiaceus</i>	Grey Kestrel
Hirundinidae	<i>Cecropis semirufa</i>	Rufous Crested Swallow
Jacanidae	<i>Actophilornis africanus</i>	African Jacana
Laniidae	<i>Lanius senator</i>	Woodchat Shrike
Malaconotidae	<i>Malaconotus blanchoti</i>	Grey Headed Bush Shrike
	<i>Dryoscopus gambensis</i>	Northern Puffback
	<i>Laniarius leucorhynchus</i>	Sooty Boubou
Meropidae	<i>Merops pusillus</i>	Little Bee Eater
	<i>Merops albicollis</i>	White Throated Bee Eater
Motacillidae	<i>Anthus leucophrys</i>	Plain Backed Pipit
	<i>Anthus trivialis</i>	Tree Pipit
	<i>Macronyx croceus</i>	Yellow Throated Lonclaw
	<i>Motacilla flava</i>	Yellow Wagtail

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name
Muscicapidae	<i>Terpsiphone rufiventer</i>	Red Billied Paradise Flycatcher
	<i>Saxicola rubetra</i>	Whinchat
Musophagidae	<i>Crinifer piscator</i>	Western Grey Plantain Eater
Nectariniidae	<i>Chalcomitra amethystina</i>	Amethyst Sunbird
	<i>Chalcomitra adelberti</i>	Buff- Throated Sunbird
	<i>Hedydipna collaris</i>	Collard Sunbird
	<i>Cyanomitra verticalis</i>	Green Headed Sunbird
	<i>Anthreptes gabonicus</i>	Mouse Brown Sunbird
	<i>Cinnyris coccinigaster</i>	splendid Sunbird
	<i>Cinnyris venustus</i>	Variable Sunbird
Passeridae	<i>Passer montanus</i>	Bush Petronia
	<i>Passer griseus</i>	Grey Headed Sparrow
Phasianidae	<i>Francolinus bicalcaratus</i>	Double Spurred Francolins
Platysteiridae	<i>Platysteira cyanea</i>	Common Wattle eye
Ploceidae	<i>Ploceus melanocephalus</i>	Black Headed Weaver
	<i>Amblyospiza albifrons</i>	Grosbeak Weaver
	<i>Euplectes franciscanus</i>	Northern Red Bishop
	<i>Malimbus erythrogaster</i>	Red Headed Malimbe
	<i>Malimbus scutatus</i>	Red Vented Malimbe
	<i>ploceus nigerrimus</i>	Viellot weaver
	<i>Ploceus cucullatus</i>	Village Weaver
Prionopidae	<i>Prionops caniceps</i>	Red Billed Helmet Shrike
Pycnonotidae	<i>Andropadus ansorgei</i>	Assorges Greenbul
	<i>Pycnonotus barbatus</i>	Common Bulbul
	<i>Andropadus virens</i>	Little Greenbul
	<i>Andropadus curvirostris</i>	Plain Greenbul
	<i>Chlorocichla simplex</i>	Simple Leaflove
	<i>Andropadus gracilirostris</i>	Slender Billed Greenbull
	<i>Andropadus virens</i>	Little Greenbull
	<i>Nicator chloris</i>	Western Nicator
	<i>Andropadus latirostris</i>	Yellow whiskered Greenbull
Rallidae	<i>Crecopsis egregia</i>	African Crake
Recurvirostridae	<i>Himantopus himantopu</i>	Black winged Sliit
Strigidae	<i>Ptilopsis leucotis</i>	Northern White faced owl
Sturnidae	<i>Lamprotornis purpureiceps</i>	purple Headed Glossy Starling
Sylviidae	<i>Sylvietta virens</i>	Green Combec
	<i>Hylia prasina</i>	Green Hylia
	<i>Eremomela pusilla</i>	Senegal Eremomela
	<i>Hyliota flavigaster</i>	Yellow Winged Hyliota
Turdidae	<i>Turdus pelios</i>	West African Thrush
Viduidae	<i>Vidua macroura</i>	Pin Tailed Whydah
Zosteropidae	<i>Platysteira concreta</i>	Yellow white Eye